

Review Article

What if Einstein was Right?" G-D's Physics" Fulfills Einstein's Quest!

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Received: 19 Oct 2023

Accepted : 23 Oct 2023

Published: 27 Oct 2023

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in further direct validation of the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Theoretical Physics is being transformed from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" (previously termed: the "Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) based following a basic "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (signified by a "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM and its inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the universe assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite two full decades of trying to do so!)) The New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm of Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is shown capable of resolving the apparent GRT-QM inconsistency, as well as completely unifying between the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", as well as between the Four Forces, thereby resolving the fundamental "Gravitational Enigma"! This fulfills Einstein's famous quest to find a singular higher "Unifying Field Theory" that could unify between GRT & QM as well as those Four basic physical features and Four Forces in a single formula! Indeed, "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm fulfills Einstein's Quest through its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec", thereby producing an extremely rapid rate of "Universal Frames" (comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal-time-point")! Empirical validation of two unique "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions" are shown which validate "G-D's Physics" as more valid than the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions, thereby "crowning" "G-D's Physics" as the New satisfactory Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics!

Introduction

Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) is considered by many as the greatest single intellectual achievement accomplished by any single individual human-being. Nevertheless, Einstein (himself) identified the basic "theoretical-inconsistency" that exists between his GRT and Quantum Mechanics (QM), and sought a "Unifying Field Theory" (UFT) that could unify between these major (macroscopic and microscopic) description of the physical reality! It is also noteworthy to note that Einstein's envisioning of such a UFT would not only be capable of resolving this apparent GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency, but also unify between the Four basic Physical features, i.e., "space", "time", "energy" and "mass" – of which his GRT was only able to unify between the "pairs" of "space-time" (e.g., as a four-dimensional continuum), "energy-mass" (based on the famous " $E=Mc^2$ " equation), and the curvature of "space-time" by certain "massive objects"; but wasn't yet capable of unifying all of these four basic physical features within a single theoretical framework. Another major problem that Einstein's quest for such a UFT touched upon is the attempt to also unify between the Four basic Forces: i.e., wherein the Gravitational Force associated with GRT – could not be unified with the other three Forces which were (later on) shown to be accounted for by the Standard Model [1-37].

In order to better understand (and appreciate) Einstein's "visionary" (and "genius") seeking of such a UFT (which seems to have "preceded his generation") has become more and more relevant 100 years after he's begun his "monumental search for such a UFT" – as it is becoming more and more clear that the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th Century's GRT & QM has reached a state of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" signified by the (above-mentioned) basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, as well as its principle inability to account for up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe assumed to comprise "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) – but which could not be detected experimentally despite two full decades of trying to detect these "elusive" DM/DE purely hypothetical concepts?! In fact, the failure of DM/DE to account for up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe points at a much more fundamental problem arising from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM: the basic assumption underlying this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of GRT & QM) is that any physical phenomenon in the universe can be explained merely based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between a finite set of factors or elements; Thus, for instance, the "Big-Bang" Model of GRT assumes that the physical universe was "created" (or "caused") by an initial nuclear event that produced all of the suns, galaxies, energy and mass in the universe, and its acceler-

ated rate of expansion is due to the (purely hypothetical) DM's/DE's direct physical interaction with those galactic elements "causing" them to be pushed "outwardly" (thereby "causing" the expansion of the physical universe). Indeed, this basic "material-causal" assumption also stands at the basis of GRT's Einstein's Equations which assume that it is the presence of certain "massive objects" that "cause" the curvature of "Space-Time", and conversely that it is this "curved Space-Time" that determines (or "causes" the "travelling-pathways" of these massive and other less-massive objects). Likewise, Quantum Mechanics is also based upon this "material-causal" assumption, wherein it is the direct physical interaction between the subatomic "probe" and "target's assumed probability wave function" that "causes" the "collapse" of this "target's probability wave function" into a singular (complimentary) "space-energy" or "mass-time" value.

But, according to one of the key theoretical postulates of a New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (previously termed: the "Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT), (e.g., which will be shown to be the new satisfactory Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century), namely: the Computational "Duality Principle" (CDP), such a "material-causal" assumption produces a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) – which inevitably leads to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy"!

The "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) Negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm

An important computational basis for this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm are two of its former Theoretical Postulates called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) and associated "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which state that it is not possible (in principle) for any two given computational elements ("x") and ("y") to determine (or "cause") the value/s of one of these elements (i.e., "y") – because such a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) would inevitably lead to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted by that Computational System's proven (empirical) capacity to determine the given 'y' element's values: Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicitly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" SRCS: it is assumed that it is only based on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Dec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec -er")?! Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec -er } → "Uec -er" or "Not Uec -er" But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome":

SRCNS: {DMDE, Uec -er } → "Not Uec -er"

In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-er ("Not Uec-er"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-er rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-er" (increased) rate of expansion! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRNCs System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-er or subsequent Not Uec-er state of the universe's acceleration rate exists?! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER)

– then this would negate the SRNC assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [38-40]?! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNCs computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRCNS: {DM/DE, Uec -er } ti → {"Not Uec -er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNCs computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti : as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec -er at ti+n ?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCNS(SRNCs) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be " Uec -er" (at ti) or " Not Uec -er" (at ti+n) ?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCNS/SRNCs Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c² /h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal timepoint"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCAER) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)!

As mentioned above, one of the significant theoretical postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm is called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which asserts that it is not possible, in principle, to compute any direct (or even indirect) relativistic or quantum physical relationship/s between any given "x" and "y" elements – from within their direct "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) assumed computational structure, but only from the higher-ordered singular "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP); This is because "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) reveals that this "problematic" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" that are

intrinsic to this SRCS computational structure; But, since in all of those Relativistic or Quantum Systems, there exists robust empirical evidence that those Systems are capable of computing the outputted result of the System, therefore the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" computing the various states and existence of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems! The most general representation of this CDP can be given as: Whenever there exists a SRCS System (of the computational structure) assuming that the whole computation is determined solely at the same "di1" computational level: SRCS {x, y} ? "y" or "Not y"/di1 the possibility of SRNCS (e.g., "negative" "Not y" output): SRNCS {x, y} ? "Not y"/di1 Inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency", since the "y" element seems to both "exist" and "not exist" at the same "di1" computational level?! SRNCS {x, y} ? "Not y"/di1 Such apparent "logical-inconsistency" also inevitably leads to an ensuing "computational indeterminacy", i.e., an apparent inability of such SRCS/SRNCS to determine whether the "y" element exists or "doesn't exist", e.g., denoting a different altered value for this "y" element?! But, since there exists specific empirical evidence for any of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems' capability to determine and output a particular "y" value, therefore this contradicts the Duality Principle's above proof that such an assumed SRCS/ SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – therefore the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (as postulated by "G-d's Physics" "Universal Computational Principle", e.g., thereby producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal-Frames", UF's at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"); Hence, below is a detailing of the various examples and manifestations of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed SRCS (& SRNCS) Computational Systems – which are all constrained and in fact negated by "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, all pointing at the "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) asserted singular higher-ordered UCP (of "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm)! a). The "Big-Bang Model": The "Big-Bang" Model represents this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction/s between a certain "Nuclear Event" (NE) and a given "exhaustive components of the Universe" exhibiting a certain "expansion state" at (U-ec/es) that "causes" the universe's expansion state to "increase", e.g., that is, be "different" than the initial "expansion state", which can be represented as:

$$\text{SRNCS } \{ \text{NE}, (\text{U-ec/es}) \} \rightarrow \text{NOT } (\text{U-ec/es}) / \text{di1}$$

Noteworthy is highlighting the implicit "material-causal" assumption of this "Big-Bang" Model's SRCS/SRNCS Computational System, e.g., whereby this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumes that it is solely based on this direct physical interaction between the NE and the initial state of the universe's expansion (U-ec/es) that this SRCS/SRNCS System is able to compute the different NOT (U-ec/es) state of the universe; Specifically that the entire SRCS/SRNCS computation exists at the same "di1" computational level of the SRCS! But, such a SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to a "logical-inconsistency":

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es)/di1?! This implies that the SRCS/ SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably also leads to an apparent "computational indeterminacy", e.g., an apparent inability of this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System to determine whether the universe will remain its initial (U-ec/e)s state or evolve into the latter " NOT (U-ec/es)"?! But, since there exists robust empirical evidence indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contempo-

rary) rate of expansion [37-45], indicates that there exists a Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – which actually increases "non-continuously" with time: " NOT (U-ec/es)"! Hence, according to the CDP, this Computational System cannot comprise the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's – but only the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational System" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec' of a series of "Universal Frames")! b). General Relativity Theory (GRT) "Einstein's Equations" Another (key) manifestation of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption is GRT's Einstein's Equations basic "material-causal" assumption: According to Einstein's Equations, the presence of certain "Massive Objects" (MO) and their direct physical interaction with "Space-Time" "causes" a change in the curvature level of this "Space-Time": SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

But, once again, such a SRNCS output of the SRCS Computational System basic computational structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", i.e., in intrinsic inability of the SRCS(SRNCS) assumed Computational System to determine whether the initial STc or the subsequent "NOT STc" state of "Space-Time" should exist – since they're both intrinsic elements within the same SRCS/SRNCS "di1" computational level!

SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1 Therefore, once again the CDP points at the ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" of such a SRNCS Computational System, which cannot decide whether the resulting state of Relativistic System should remain at the initial STc state or undergo an additional curvature of Space-Time as in the more "curved Space-Time" state, e.g., signified by "NOT STc"?! But, since the abovementioned clear empirical indication of the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [37-45], represents a "special-case" of GRT's Einstein's Equations, then this indicates that the Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (associated with Einstein's abovementioned SRCS/SRNCS assumed Computational System); Therefore, once again, the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features -of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", giving rise to an extremely rapid series of UF's frames; Indeed, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm was shown to offer an alternative computational account for the apparent "material-causal" "curvature of Space-Time by massive objects" – i.e., based on "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features by this singular higher-ordered UCP, and the new "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these four basic physical features of the universe:

$$\mathbf{S: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] + \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\} \text{ such that: } f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n) \leq f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i...n)]}$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to

the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: \{f\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]\} / c * n \{UF's\} \text{ poaj.orj poaj.org Journal of Theoretical and Computational Physics 2022 Page no: 11 such that: } f\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] > f\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i\dots n)]$$

Where in the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that: $M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{[UF's(i\dots n)]$ Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{[UF's(i\dots n)]$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF): c). Quantum Mechanics "Material-Causal" Assumed Collapse of the Target's Probability Wave-Function: Another important manifestation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption which is challenged and negated by "G-d's Physics" New "Computational Duality Principle" is Quantum Mechanics' "material-causal" assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction between a given subatomic "probe" (P) element and a corresponding subatomic ("un-collapsed") "target's probability wave-function" (Tu-wf) – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse of the probability wave-function" into a single "complimentary" (space/energy or time/mass) value:

$$SRNCS: \{P, Tu-wf\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/di1$$

But, as stated above, according to the CDP such a SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy":

$$SRNCS: \{P, Tu-wf\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/di1$$

Wherein this assumed SRNCS Computational System cannot decide

whether the target element should exhibit its assumed "un-collapsed" probability wave function values or the single "complimentary" (space/energy or mass/time) "collapsed" value?! However, since we know empirically that any such QM System is capable of determining the "collapsed" single complimentary value of any given subatomic target element – therefore the CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe as an extremely rapid series of Universal Frames (UF's) at the incredible rate of "c² /h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! As outlined and delineated extensively (previously) the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm expands, embeds and transcends the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of QM's "single spatial-temporal" "particle", "multiple spatial-temporal" "wave" – and "exhaustive" "Universal Frames" (UF's) computational perspectives which are all embedded within the UCP's singular higher-ordered (integrated) "Universal Computational Formula" (outlined above).

The Unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"!?

Hence, we realize that based upon the CDP's negation of the basic SRCS/SRNCS computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., including a principle negation of Einstein's Equations' (three) EEE's (comprising) the Big-Bang Model, DM/DE and the Cosmological Constant) SRCS/SRNCS computational system – which (as shown above and demonstrated previously) inevitably leads to both "logical inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" which are negated by the universe's (apparent SRCS/SRNCS Computational System) to determine its accelerated rate of expansion; therefore the CDP unequivocally points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle", which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four basic physical features) comprising the entire physical universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s!

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" discovery of this singular higher-ordered UCP and particularly two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions": "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent") – whose four possible combinations yield the UCP's computation of each of the four basic physical features: i.e., Frame- consistent ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"); and "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") (e.g., simultaneously for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the whole UF frame, for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! Intriguingly, this entirely new "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) theoretical framework opens an exciting "new window" to try and resolve the two major problems of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (e.g., indicating the "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm) – which alongside with "G-D's Physics" (subsequent) capability to empirically validate (at least one) of its unique "Critical Prediction/s", as more valid than the corresponding prediction/s of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM; will unequivocally "crown" the New "G-D's Physics" as the New satisfactory Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) [1-47]! This "Paradigmatic-Shift" inevitably followed the appearance of a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm signified by a basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)! Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on its

discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ” (!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF’s frames comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!

According to Thomas Kuhn’s [50], well-accepted analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions” [50], in order for Science to accept such a “Paradigmatic-Shift” (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a “theoretical-inconsistency” between the “pillars” of the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm’s discovery of the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle’s” (UCP’s) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all “Single Spatial-Temporal” (SST) “particle/objects”; “Multiple Spatial-Temporal” (MST) “wave-phenomena”; and “Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal” “Universal Frame/s” computations! In this manner, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” (SLB) as opposed to QM’s “Quantum Entanglement” phenomena’s implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic “entangled particle’s” (“complimentary pairs” value may “instantaneously” affect the other “entangled particle’s” complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to “G-D’s Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more “constrictive” UCP’s MST and SST computations, the apparent “Quantum Entanglement” phenomenon merely represents the UCP’s computation of “equivalent SST particle points” along the MST’s (subatomic) “wave” computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP’s computation! Alongside “G-D’s Physics” new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” is based on the UCP’s two (out of three) “Computational Dimensions” i.e., “Framework” and “Consistency” four possible combinations: “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), and “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) possible combinations! Hence, “G-D’s Physics” new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT’s strict SLB’s principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement’s “instantaneous” effect of the measurement of one entangled particle’s complimentary pairs’ measurement upon the other entangled particle’s complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of “G-D’s Physics” (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP’s computation of “equivalent MST wave” “particle-points”, coupled with its two “Computational Dimensions” complimentary exhaustive UCP’s computation of

“Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”), which can account for the apparent “entanglement” of two such “equivalent SST particle points” along the “MST wave” (simultaneous) computation of the UCP’s “complimentary-exhaustive” “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) “complimentary pairs”!

Likewise, the New “G-D’s Physics” theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe’s empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of “G-D’s Physics” is based on its (novel) “Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis” (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP), then this brings about an “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” (New Year) two days’ special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an “UNCIARE” increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique “Critical Prediction” which can differentiate the prediction of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM: according to Kuhn’s [50] analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”, in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm to the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique “Critical Prediction” that can differentiate the predictions of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s and QM’s predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) “Critical Prediction” of the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm is verified as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s predictions – then (according to Kuhn’s 50 well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New “G-D’s Physics” as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we’ve been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results:

In order to directly contrast between the New “G-d’s Physics” (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, “G-d’s Physics” identified a unique “Critical-Prediction” stemming from its new “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time” – based on the UCP’s singular higher-ordered two “Computational Dimensions” of “Framework” (frame/object) and “Consistency” (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP’s Computational Dimensions definition of the “mass” of any given particle as an “object-consistent” computational measure:

$$M: \Sigma \{O_i\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP’s computational measure of the “mass” value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the “Object-consistent” “internal” {o-x, o-y, o-z} values across a given series of UF’s frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54-56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al. [54-56] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\}) / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+51$; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with

the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion 58-61?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

Based on the unequivocal experimental results (above) indicating that the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) two (unique) "Critical Predictions" were verified experimentally and found to be more accurate than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: regarding the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE), and related to the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings; it becomes clear that the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying (20th century) GRT & QM! Moreover, it has been previously shown that this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm can also resolve the apparent basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels

in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") Indeed, based on "G-D's Physics" discovery of this singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") for every consecutive UF's frame/s, a novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) has been discovered which completely unifies – i.e., for the first time in Physics, between those four basic physical features!

As known, Einstein's GRT was only capable of unifying between the "pairs" of "space" and "time" (which become a four-dimensional Space-Time), and between "energy" and "mass" (known as the famous Energy-Mass Equivalence, " $E = Mc^2$ "), as well as GRT's Einstein's Equations' assertion that "massive objects" curve this "Space-Time" etc. But, thus far, Physics was not able to completely unify between those four basic physical features?! Indeed, "stemming" from this basic inability to unify between the four basic physical features ensues what can be termed as the "Gravitational Enigma"?!?

Resolving the "Gravitational Enigma":

Indeed, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm reformulation of these four basic physical features based on their simultaneous computation by this singular higher-ordered UCP was shown capable of resolving the apparent GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency" and in fact completely integrate between these four basic physical features, e.g., of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", as well as between the Four basic Physical Forces as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular higher-ordered UCP! In this manner, the basic "unresolved" "Gravitational Enigma" of Modern Physics – which Einstein sought to resolve through his ("unwavering") quest for a singular Unifying Field Theory is being resolved by the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm which is being unequivocally empirically validated in this article!

Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: *Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can:* a) *Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm);* Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm [1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ "), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel

"computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's series) (Figure 1):

FIGURE 1: UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

FIGURE 2: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ \hline h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [Px1 (a...z)]

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} E * s \\ \hline t \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} M * c^2 \\ \hline h \end{array} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} \left. \left. \begin{array}{c} t * m = h * \\ s * e \end{array} \right. \right. \right\} c^2$$

in which “Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle’s” (“complimentary pairs”) are embedded as “special cases” within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of “G-D’S PHYSICS” or G-D’S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm’s potential resolution of the GE’s first component – i.e., a) *Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of “gravitation” which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM)*; is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP’s (in-depth) analysis of the (true) “computational basis” of the “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D’S PHYSICS’s computational analysis, this “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” for the transmission of any “signal” (or even “information”) across “space” and “time” – which seems to be “contradicted” by QM’s “Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon”, indicating that the measurement of one “entangled particle” “instantaneously” affects the “complimentary” (“space/energy” or “mass/time”) measurement of the other “entangled particle”?! But, according to the new CUT’s Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and “resolution”- of this apparent “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from the UCP’s singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all “Single Spatial-Temporal” computation (“SST”): “particle” of relativistic “object” (e.g., relating to only “one” spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), “Multi Spatial-Temporal” computation (MST): “wave” (e.g., relating to at least “two” points being measured at any point in time) or “Exhaustive Spatial Temporal” (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all “exhaustive” spatial pixels comprising an entire “Universal Frame”, UF), across a series of UF’s frames (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3: UCP’S “SST”, “MST” & “EST” COMPUTATIONS

UCP’s	SST	MST	EST
Computations			
Num. “ST” Points	1	2+	All Points

In order to advance towards demonstrating in what manner can this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm address and resolve the “second” (abovementioned) facet of the GE, we must now validate a unique “Critical Prediction” of this New G-D’S PHYSICS – as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying GRT & QM!

Based on the clear empirical validations of this unique Critical Prediction of “G-D’S PHYSICS” as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein G-D’S PHYSICS is recognized as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics! Based upon Thomas Kuhn’s³¹ (well-known) analysis of occurrence of “Paradigmatic-Shifts” (in any particular scientific discipline), the acceptance of the New G-D’S PHYSICS as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm may be equivalent to the acceptance of Einstein’s GRT as the New

Scientific Paradigm for Twentieth Century Physics – also based on such an empirical validation of a unique “Critical Prediction” associated with GRT (e.g., Mercury’s “double-valued” perihelion pathway around the Sun due to the curvature of “Space-Time” by the Sun’s mass etc.).

As such, the New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm completely unifies between these four basic physical features (of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”) – e.g., for the first time in Theoretical Physics, since Einstein’s GRT was able to unify only between “space” and “energy” as “a four dimensional “Space-Time” continuum, and between “energy” and “mass” through the famous “Energy-Mass Equivalence”, and connect between certain “massive objects” as “curving Space-Time”; but not yet (completely) integrate these four basic physical features within a singular UCF! Indeed, this complete unification of those four basic physical features as secondary computational “by-products” of the same singular UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) offer us an alternative conceptualization of the manner in which this singular UCP completely integrates the Four Forces: This is because these Four Forces – Weak and Strong Nuclear Forces, the Electromagnetic Force and the Gravitational Force all represent different aspects of this singular UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features, which are all integrated by the G-D’S PHYSICS’s New “Universal Computational Formula”!

Specifically, the UCP re-explains the “Gravitational Force” as merely representing its differential computation of relatively “High-Mass; Low energy” (HMLE) vs. “low-mass; high-energy” (LMHE) objects (particles): According to the New G-D’S PHYSICS, it is suggested that the UCP “differentially computes” the HMLE particles as occupying relatively “stable regions” within each consecutive UF’s frame/s, whereas those LMHE particles seem to “alternate” their “spatial position” (across the series of UF’s frames), they creating “unstable regions” (within those UF’s frames’ series)!? Hence, what “appears” as a “curvature of Space-Time” around “massive objects” (HMLE) – (truly) only represents the UCP’s “differential computation” of those HMLE “stable regions” of the UF’s which are surrounded by the relatively “less stable regions” (LMHE)! Indeed, an indirect empirical support for this New G-D’S PHYSICS’s “alternative explanation” for the “Gravitational Force” was also given (in this article) through its unique “Critical Prediction” confirmation given through the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings [41-43]; indicating that based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’s computational definition of “mass” as an “Object-consistent” measure, the relatively “more-massive” Muon (negatively charged) particle (which “sinks” into the Proton of the “Muon-replaced Hydrogen Atom”) “causing” it to become more “spatially-consistent” than the equivalent “Standard Hydrogen Proton” (which is not “conjoined” with the “lighter electron” particle)! These “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings failed to be explained based on the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying QM (and GRT; e.g., despite various attempts to explain this “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings: the “three-body force”[40], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavor-dependent interaction [38,39], higher dimension gravity [44], a new boson [45])! In other words, the G-D’S PHYSICS’s new “computational definitions” of the manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP computes the “mass” of any given particle (such as the “more massive” Muon particle), relatively to a “less massive” particle (such as the “electron”) perfectly explains the significant reduction in the Hydrogen’s Proton Radius (e.g., “spatial consistency”), when surrounded by the Muon as opposed to when surrounded by the electron!

Therefore, the G-D’S PHYSICS’s discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features, alongside its novel “computational definitions” for each of those physical features – elegantly resolves the four different “facets” of the GE: a) *Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM)* – based on the UCP’s simultaneous computation of SST “particles” as embedded within “MST-wave” computation (thereby resolving the apparent contradiction between the “Speed

of Light Barrier” and the “quantum entanglement” phenomenon); b) *Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion (that is not based on the purely hypothetical “Dark-Matter” (DM) concept) – based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’S stipulated and empirically validated “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE), associated with the G-D’S PHYSICS’S newly discovered UCP and its connection with a “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (at “special time intervals” such as the JRH two days’ time interval);* c) *Unify between the “Gravitational Force” and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force! – based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’S newly discovered UCF, and associated novel UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features.* d) *Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the “curvature of Space-Time” by “massive objects” (based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’S New Scientific “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm) – based on the UCP’s “differential computation” of relatively “stable regions” of “HMLE objects” surrounded by relatively “less stable regions” of “LMHE regions” (pointing at the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features)! Indeed, the potential significance (and “beauty”) of the G-D’S PHYSICS’S (novel) resolution of the GE stems not only from its broad “relevance” to such “diverse facets” (of the GE) as the unification of the (macroscopic) GRT & (subatomic) QM realms, the unification of the Four Forces, offering an alternative (exciting) explanations for the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion (while “discarding” DM as “superfluous”, i.e., “non-existent”!) and the “curvature of Space-Time” (based on the UCP’s differential computation of HMLE vs. LMHE); but perhaps even more significantly in offering 21st century Theoretical Physics a new “A-Causal Computation” G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm that is able to completely unify the four basic physical features within a singular (novel) “Universal Computational Formula” based on the major discovery of the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features!*

Over and beyond fulfilling Einstein's ("historic") quest for unifying between GRT & QM, and succeeding in completely unifying between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", as well as between the Four Forces! "G-D's Physics New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics advances our basic knowledge and understanding of the "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe – as governed solely by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "pre-planned" the whole "origination"- "development"- and even "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, i.e., a state in which Humanity and Science recognize this singularity of the UCP/UCR including its unique "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's (and Science's) existence and behavior!

A Brief Summary of several major "G-D's Physics" Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

b) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives

the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

c) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה")

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah " State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah ' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular

reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past" - "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/ חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A

"Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Gevorah"/גבורה):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" in order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Tiferet"/תפארת):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "spe-

cial-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification-or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva" (תשובה)/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva"/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral

action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yesod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" ("מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinite" ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s!) It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yesod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent"

(energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר" / "Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of

the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר" / "Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר" / "Keter-Infinitude" ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)" for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

One of the clear theoretical distinctions between the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm and the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm has to do with their diametrically opposed theoretical conceptions of the “origin” of the universe – and likewise, the “evolution” and also (stipulated) “end-state” of the physical universe! According to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (underlying GRT & QM) every phenomena in the physical universe – including its hypothesized initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event occurs merely based on (“random”: direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between certain material or physical elements, forces (e.g., such as GRT’s assumed direct “material-causal” physical interactions between certain “massive objects” and their assumed “causing” of the “curvature of ‘Space-Time’ etc.) or between certain physical properties of given subatomic particles (e.g., such as the direct physical interaction/s between a given subatomic “probe” particle and its corresponding assumed “target’s probability wave function” – which is assumed to “cause” the “collapse” of this “probability wave function” into a singular “complimentary”: “space-energy”, or “mass-time” value); In contrast, according to the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT), any such (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction is strictly negated – based on its basic discovery of the “simultaneity” of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., for every consecutive UF’s frame/s), and the complete “dissolution” of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s back into the singularity of this UCP! Therefore, according to the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the “same” or “different” UF’s frame/s, thereby negating the very basic assumption underlying the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (of GRT & QM)!

Ensuing from this profound discovery of this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is its negation of some of the most fundamental tenets of this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm: a) Negation of the “Big-Bang” Model associated with GRT! Based on the above-mentioned “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm’s insistence upon the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s), the basic assumption wherein the physical universe was created by an initial “Big-Bang” initial nuclear event is strictly negated: since the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe), there could not have been any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any such stipulated initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event and the creation of all the suns, galaxies, matter, energy space or time (e.g., assumed to have happened as “caused” by this initially assumed nuclear event)?! This is simply because at none of the UF’s – the “first”, “second”... Trillionth... Nth UF’s frame/s from the beginning of this stipulated “Big-Bang” nuclear event (e.g., and until the “present” UF’s frame/s) can there exist any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – due to the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s)! Moreover, since all of these exhaustive spatial pixels “dissolve” back into the singularity of this UCP (“in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s), therefore there cannot also exist any “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels that exist in any two consecutive UF’s frame/s!

So, we find that according to the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm the universe could not have been created (or “caused”) by any such (initial) “Big-Bang” nuclear event! Likewise, GRT’s conception of the continuous accelerated expansion of the universe – as “caused” by the purely hypothetical “dark-matter”, (e.g., assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be detected despite two full decades of intensive experimentations trying to do so?!); is also strictly negated

by the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm! This is because, once again, even if such (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” could exist (somehow), its assumed direct “material-causal” physical interaction/s with certain galactic elements in the universe, i.e., “causing” them to “expulse” from each other, thereby creating the accelerated expansion of the universe – is negated by “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal” Computation Paradigm, which asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., existing either in the “same” or “different” UF’s frames (as noted above)!

A “Gimatria-Based Consistency Computation” of Objects!

Based on the discovery of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, and its shown capacity to resolve the apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and more importantly, its empirical validation of two of its unique “Critical Predictions”, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM; we now reach another “pivotal point” along the development of this New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm of 21st century Theoretical Physics: Since the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm stipulated an “A-Causal Computation” stemming from the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, which points at the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, existing either in the same- or different UF’s frame/s, then this points at the need for this singular higher-ordered UCP to compute all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe) for each consecutive UF’s frame/s! However, thus far, the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm’s discovered “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions’ Universal Computational Formula” (THCD-UCF) was only capable of explaining (in general terms) the UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) based on its stipulated two (out of three) “Computational Dimensions” (of “Consistency” and “Framework”) combinations! In other words, those four basic physical features are computed by this singular UCP as “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or as “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) computational measures of the degree of “consistency” or “inconsistency” of any given exhaustive spatial pixel’s “object” across a series of UF’s frames!

Moreover, the general (overall) conception of the origination- sustenance- and “Ultimate Goal” of the universe’s development by this singular UCP has given us an overall (good) overall understanding of the general framework for “G-D’s Physics” New scientific explanation of the universe’s existence and development; What’s still “missing” is a “minute-detailed” understanding of the manner in which this UCP “differentiates” between its computation of these four basic physical features for every individual “object”, i.e., “inanimate” or “animate”! The suggested new “Gimatria Consistency Computation” (GCC) “fills” this “gap” and offers a new conceptual explanation for the manner in which this UCP can compute those four basic physical features (e.g., as “differentiating” their values for any specific “inanimate” or “animate” object)! The basic assumption underlying this new “GCC” facet of “G-D’s Physics” THCD-UCF is that based on the (Hebrew) Alphabet’s “naming” of every such (“animate” or “inanimate”) object, the UCP computes those four (integrated) basic physical features, e.g., through the usage of the five (subsequent) HCD (following the initial three “General Plan” of the UCP’s origination and development of the physical universe, i.e., of “Wisdom”/“חכמה”, “Computation”/“הניב” & “Reversed Time Geulah Goal Consistency”/“דעת”)!)

These five subsequent HCD comprise of: “Chessed”, “Gevorah”, “Tiferet”, “Neztach” & “Hod”, which are each stipulated to be comprised of the “ten total HCD’s ten “zero’s” minute temporal computation of the UCP – totaling the UCP’s overall rate of computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s)! In other words, the manner in which

the UCP can compute each and every exhaustive spatial pixel object's four basic physical features is based on a combination of its unique "name" – according to its "Gimateria" computation, based on those "subsequent five" ("Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" HCD) detailing of each of the given "name's" (Hebrew) letters equivalent numeric value!

In other words, we obtain (e.g., for the first time in Theoretical Physics) a "Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation" (NMGCC) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe! This new "G-D's Physics" NMGCC conception of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP is capable of computing each and every "object" in the physical universe – based on its "Gimateria" (Hebrew Letters' numerical value) as representing the number of times that every exhaustive spatial pixel is presented across a certain series of UF's frames! Since we've already seen, that the UCP computes the "mass" value of any given object as its computation of the number of times this object has been presented (as "spatially-consistent") across a series of UF's frames! This means that the current discovery of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm's "NMGCC" capability of the UCP to "translate" the given "Gimateria" numerical value of any given "object's" (Hebrew) name into the UCP's computation of the five "secondary-essential" Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD): "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod", such that each of these HCD possesses all ten HCD's corresponding to "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" representing the rate of the UCP's overall rate of UF's computation, i.e., $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! This means for instance, that the Hebrew letters for the word "human-being" "אדם" comprise these three letters "א", "ד", "ם" which correspond to the "Gimatria" of "1-[1-10]", "4-[11-20]" & "40-[21-30]" denoting the cumulative number of times that a "human-being" is presented across a series of UF's frames – with a special significance for the corresponding unique Gimateria numerical value for each of those (potential) five "secondary-essential" HCD ("Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod"! In other words, the specific (Hebrew) "Gimatria" for a "human-being" comprises a very unique and specific composition of three (out of the five) "secondary-essential" HCD: "Chessed", "Gevurah" & "Tiferet", with each one of them possessing a specific numerical value which can be translated to the UCP's computation of a human-being's "mass", or in fact any other of the four (completely integrated) basic physical features (of "time", "space" or "energy"), based on the earlier mentioned "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF):

Noteworthy is the fact that we can perhaps "infer" some of these four basic physical features based on the specific HCD's comprising each "object" – such as for instance, in the case of the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of a "human-being" based on his Hebrew names specific "Gimateria" (three initial) HCD's numerical values, and understanding of the "corresponding" HCD's key characteristics: for instance, the fact that "אדם" only possesses the three initial HCD's of "Chessed", "Gevurah" & "Tiferet" (but not the two subsequent "Neztach" & "Hod" HCD), indicating that the UCP's computation of a "human-being" corresponding to the UCP characteristics of "Chessed": its natural tendency to "give" or to "nurture" (and "grow"), "Gevurah": the UCP's tendency to "measure" and "limit" its "giving" and "nurturance"; & "Tiferet": The UCP's capacity to "balance" and "integrate" between these apparently "opposing" ("Chessed" & "Gevurah") UCD (with a leaning towards the "Chessed" HCD in this "Tiferet" HCD)! More specifically, these three "Gimatria" Hebrew Letters' specific numerical value also indicates the relative significance of each of these three (initial HCD: "Chessed", "Gevurah" & "Tiferet"): Thus, for instance, the fact that amongst these three initial three HCD, it is primarily the "Tiferet" HCD which possesses the highest numerical value: "40-30" (sec!) implies the UCP's computation of a "human-being" is based upon the unique capacity of human-beings to "integrate" between the first letter of "א" associated with "Chessed": characterized by the Hebrew first letter "א" – which also represents "G-D" (since the Hebrew word for "G-D" is

"אלוקים" which begins with this same "א" (Alef) letter and which is characterized by: "Goodness", "Giving", "Spirituality" etc.; and the second letter of "ד" (which also stands for the Hebrew word for "blood" signifying the "human body" – such that this integration of the "physical bodily" element with the "Divine" ("Spiritual") element is achieved and is also "leaning towards expressing" (more) the Divine element!

Interestingly, the Hebrew word for "Earth" or "soil" is very similar to Hebrew word for a "human-being" "אדמה" which has the addition of a fourth letter "ה" associated with the fourth "Secondary-essential" (five) "HCD's": "Neztach" נצח which signifies the UCP's capacity to "overcome any obstacle/s" for the fulfillment of its ultimate "Geulah Goal" of obtaining a "Perfected": "Moral" & "Spiritual" state of Humanity and the universe! This may imply that whereas a "human-being" is embedded with the characteristics of his ability to "integrate" and "uplift" his "bodily-material" nature with his "Divine" aspect, i.e., based on his given "Gevurah" and "Tiferet" HCD's; in the case of the Hebrew word for "Earth", the UCP adds the fourth HCD of "Neztach" which allows the "Earth" to serve as a "vehicle" to "manifest" and "overcome" any "obstacles" for the fulfillment of the UCP's ultimate "Geulah Goal Perfected State" of Humanity and of the universe!

Another pertinent example of the significance of this (newly discovered) "G-D's Physics" "Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation" (NMGCC) may be the Hebrew word for "G-D": "אלוקים" which comprises all of those "five" "secondary-essential" HCD's letters! Once again the first letter of the "Chessed" Dimension is "א" (Alef) which signifies not only the first letter of the Alphabet, but also represents "G-D"! The second letter is "ל" which represents the "Gevurah" HCD ("G-D's" "fierce force" of "overcoming any obstacles"); "ה" 5" in "Gimatria" for the third letter corresponding to the third "Tiferet" HCD signifying the UCP's capacity to "integrate" the five HCD's (as well as signifying the "third initial HCD's of "Binah" or "Computation, i.e., the UCP's capacity to organize, plan and compute the entire "Blue-Print Plan" of the whole development of the universe from its "inanimate" (initial) manifestation through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" Perfected state of the universe)! The fourth letter is "ד" ("Yud" ("י") standing for the "Neztach" HCD which is the UCP's ability to "overcome" and "triumph" over any "obstacles" in order to advance the whole universe towards its Ultimate "Geulah Goal Perfected" State! This is significant, because the "Yud" letter also characterizes "G-D" (e.g., appearing as the first letter in G-D's holy name), and possesses the "Gimatria" (10) representing the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (which points at the fact that the UCP's capacity of "overcoming" and "obstacle/s" for the fulfillment of its Ultimate "Geulah-Goal Perfected State" of the universe stems from its THCD's overall "Blueprint Plan" and its execution towards attaining this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal"! The final (sixth) letter is "ם" for the fifth HCD of "Hod" which signifies (according to "G-D's Physics THCD) the UCP's enabling us as human-beings to do "Teshuva" (e.g., ask for "forgiveness" and "understanding" from "G-D", preceded by our conscious decision to "change our behavior" (for the better), and try our best not to "repeat" any "moral misdeeds"; This fifth "Hod" HCD also encompasses the aspect of us as human-beings recognizing the "Beauty", "Perfection" and "All-Goodness" of "G-D"!

So, we can see that the UCP's computation of every (possible) "object" (i.e., "inanimate" or "animate") is based upon its "Gimatria" of the Hebrew letters: e.g., which possess both significance in terms of the five "secondary-essential" Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) to which they belong (according to their order: the first letter belonging to the "Chessed"; second to "Gevurah" etc.) and their relative "Gimatria strength", e.g., both in terms of each Hebrew letter's "numerical value" and their associated HCD's value (i.e., "Chessed": from -1-10; "Gevurah": from -11 – 20; "Tiferet": from -21 – 30; "Neztach": -31 – 40 ; "Hod": from -41 – 50 !)

Hence, an emerging new facet of this new NMGCC discovery made by “G-D’s Physics” is the transformation of these Hebrew letters’ “Gimatria”: e.g., “numerical value” of each letter, combined with its association with each of those respective five “secondary-essential” HCD’s – as determining the number of times that this object will be presented across a series of UF’s frames: which would determine its “mass” value(!) But, as we’ve seen, another (not less important) facet of this (newly discovered) NMGCC is the relative significance of each of the letters/specific HCD (based on its Gimatria & HCD’s “zero’s strength”, as “glanced” from the above examples) pertaining to each object’s (Hebrew) letters.

One more significant discovery associated with this (novel) NMGCC perspective on how the UCP (continuously and simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe relates to those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s differentiation between “human-beings”, which possess a “free Moral Choice” and all other “inanimate and animate” forms which do not possess this “free Moral Choice”! This is due to the fact that the execution of those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s depends on the UCP’s “allowance” (and in fact “pre-planning”) for human-beings to make those (precise) “free Moral Choice/s” as a part of its (overall) “Ultimate Geulah Goal”, e.g., of “steering” Humanity (and the whole physical universe) towards that “Perfected Geulah State”, in which all human-beings (and Humanity, as a whole) will recognize the “Oneness” of this singular “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (or “Universal Consciousness Reality”), its innate characters of “Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, and our “inseparability” from It (and from each other)! Indeed, when we (closely) examine those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s we can sense that they are all “centered” or “anchored” in the UCP’s “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP), e.g., whose “sole-aim” is to “teach” us (human-beings) our “inseparability” from this singular (higher-ordered) UCP – through our “free Moral Choice”! Thus, the “first” amongst those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s is “Chessed’s” “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP)! This DEMP states that whenever any Individual human-being chooses an “Immoral Choice”, e.g., towards another Individual human-being, which causes “pain” or “suffering” (“G-d forbid”), then this necessarily “triggers” the UCP’s selection of an “equivalent negative situation”, in which that Individual human-being that inflicted “pain/suffering” would have to “experience” the same “negative situation” – in order for us to realize that such “Immoral Choice/s” is not “right” and should be “avoided”! “Implicitly”, since we begin “realizing” the “connection” that exists between any (negative) “Immoral Choice” that we may have made – and our own experiencing of such a “negative situation” (e.g., of “pain or suffering”, “G-d forbid”), then this raises our “understanding” and “awareness” that we cannot make any such “Immoral Choices” but rather must “correct” our own “free Moral Choice/s” to constitute “positive Moral Choice/s”! (Once again, this implicit “Moral understanding” or “Moral awareness” that our “Moral/Immoral Choices” determine the “Moral/Immoral” “positive” or “negative” situations that we would experience (ourselves) makes us realize that we are really “inseparable” from each other, as “integral parts of this singular higher-ordered UCP!” Following this “Chessed’s” (HCD) “Dynamic-Equilibrium is the next HCD: “Gevurah” which possesses a “Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir” of all “past”, “present” and “multiple possible future/s” – for each Individual human-being depending upon (his or her) Moral/Immoral Choices (at each point in time), which already manifests the UCP’s computation of the specific future for each individual human-being based on their specific Moral Choice/s; Next, follows the “Tiferet” HCD’s Collective Human Consciousness Focus Jewish “Rosh Hashanah” (CHCF-JRH) “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe” (NCAEU), in which the UCP essentially computes the specific “future/s” UF’s for all Individual human-beings for the entire next year (and which also correlates to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus’ “triggering” a “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe”); Then, follows the HCD’s of “Neztach’s” “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”, corresponding to actually

computed (next) “future UF’s” value/s for each Individual human-being (based upon the previous HD’s computation of the DEMP’s precise selected future for each Individual human-being etc.); and finally, the “fifth” HCD of “Hod’s” “UCP’s Teshuva”, in which the UCP allows for a “Teshuva” of each Individual human-being (for any “Immoral Choices/s” they have may made) which then would “prevent” the materialization of any potentially “negative state” (computed at the previous Neztach’s “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”)! So, we can see, that these “five-essential” HCD’s are (indeed) “centered” around the human capacity to select “Moral/Immoral Choices” based on the “free Moral Choice” (unique) characteristic of human-beings (e.g., unlike any other “inanimate” or “animate”: “plants” or “animals”);

Once again, the UCP’s “motivation” underlying these “five-essential” HCD’s is closely related to the fulfillment of the UCP’s overall “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of steering the entire physical universe towards its “Perfected Geulah State” (e.g., “Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically”)! Since the whole “aim” and “Goal” of the universe’s creation- sustenance- and evolution- by this singular higher-ordered UCP is to evolve the whole universe from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: animals, plants and human-beings to the Ultimate “Geulah Goal” of the whole of Humanity realizing the singularity of this “Universal Computational/Consciousness Reality”, including its unique characteristics of the Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP), “All-Goodness”, “Peace and Harmony”; therefore those “five-essential HCD’s assist in “steering” Humanity (as a whole – as well as each Individual human-being) towards the attainment of this “Perfected Geulah Goal” State, through our experiencing of the “equivalent positive/negative state/s” produced by our Moral (or “G-d forbid”) Immoral Choice/s, and our ability to make “Teshuva” or to “learn” from those “negative” (“Immoral Choice/s” ensued) or “positive” (“Moral Choice/s produced) Choices! Interestingly, this new NMGCC discovery of “G-D’s Physics” new manner in which the UCP’s actually computes each and every object’s “Gimateria-based” (Hebrew letters’ numerical value – as associated with these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s) is found to differentiate between the manner in which the UCP utilizes these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s – for human-beings (e.g., possessing a “free Moral Choice”) as opposed to the other “Non-Human”, e.g., “inanimate” and “animate”: plants and animals: As noted above, for human beings, the UCP’s utilization of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s is aimed at “teaching” and “perfecting” our Moral nature such that we realize through these five “secondary-essential” HCD’s our “inseparability” from each other as well as from this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), which is a part of the overall UCP’s advancement of Humanity (and the universe) towards the fulfillment of its “Ultimate Geulah Perfect-ed Moral & Spiritual State”! Hence, in order to “teach” and “perfect” each and every Individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) through the operation of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s the UCP utilizes each one of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s based on each of these five HCD’s “ten zero’s” – as corresponding to the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD’s)! This implies that in addition to the “basic” Gimatria Consistency Computation (GCC) pertaining to each one of the letters comprising each Individual human-being’s “name” (and the more general GCC of the “general name” of a “human-being”, as discussed above), for each Individual human-being, based on (his or her) “Moral/Immoral Choice/s” (as discussed above) the UCP computes for each one of the 10 zero’s corresponding to each of those five “secondary-essential” the THCD’s complete “Moral rectification”! In contrast, for all “Non-Human” (NH) forms of “inanimate” matter or “animate”: plants and animals, the UCP computes only the GCC based computation of these five “secondary-essential” (as discussed above) based only on the Gimateria (Hebrew letters numerical values associated with each one of these five “secondary-essential” ten zero’s values), i.e., without connection to the THCD’s overall Moral rectification)! One “exception” to this “neutrality” of the THCD’s association with the “ten zero’s” for “Non-Human” (NH) forms

(of “inanimate” matter, “animate”: plants and animals) is all instances in which these NH objects are associated (in some form or fashion) to a Moral/Immoral Choice/s that a given Individual human-being has made, in which case it is possible that that NH “object” will be “included” or “affected” by that Individual human-being’s Moral/Immoral Choice/s (e.g., as manifesting through the human DEMP’s associated five “secondary-essential” HCD’s “ten-zero’s”)!

Thus, we see that the manner in which the UCP computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels (and “objects”) in the universe based on a “Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation” is “non-material” (in nature)! As we’ve seen previously, due to the “A-Causal Computation” characterization of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm (e.g., stemming from the fact that there cannot exist any direct or indirect “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF’s frames due to the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF’s frame/s and the complete “dissolution” of the whole universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s); we’ve realized that since there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two (or more exhaustive) spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frames, therefore there cannot be any “transference” or “effects” across any two consecutive UF’s frames: in other words, one UF’s cannot “affect” or “create” any “effect” or “influence” upon its subsequent UF’s frame/s! Instead, we have to look at the singular higher-ordered UCP – not only as the sole and singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” existing both “during” each of its consecutively produced UF’s frame/s, and also solely existing “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s, as the “Computational Invariance Principle” (of “G-D’s Physics New Scientific Paradigm” teaches us; But even beyond that, we realize (in this article) that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle (or Universal Consciousness Reality) computes each and every exhaustive spatial pixel’s object in the universe depends entirely upon this singular UCP’s Gimatria based (Hebrew letters) Consistency Computation, which is “guided” based on the UCP’s or “Universal Consciousness Reality’s (UCR) overall “pre-planned” Blueprint for progressing the entire physical universe from inanimate “matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-being towards the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the “Oneness”, “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” of this singular higher ordered Universal Consciousness Reality! We’ve discovered in this (unique) article that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR continuously creates- “dissolved”- re-computes- and evolves- every exhaustive spatial-pixel and object in the universe based on this NMGCC computation which differentiates between Human (H) and Non-Human (NH: “inanimate” matter, or “animate”: plants and animals) by incorporating (in addition to the basic Gimateria based computation of every object’s Hebrew name as associated with those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s ten zero’s numerical value etc.) also the DEMP’s manifestation through those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s THCD’s Moral rectification associated with the “ten-respective zero’s”! We thus obtain an entirely new conception of the true nature of the physical universe – which is essentially “non-material”: it is only a manifestation of the singular higher-ordered UCR (which constitutes the only “constant”, “uniform” and “continuous” reality existing both “during” its production of each consecutive UF’s frames comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels of the universe, as well as existing solely without the presence of any physical universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frames), which has “pre-planned” the whole origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate “Perfected Geulah Goal” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this “Universal Consciousness Reality” characterized by “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

A New “Gimatria-Based” Continuous Creation of the Universe’s “Matter”!

But, even beyond the profound unification of those four basic physical features through “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm’s “Universal Computational Formula”, and its capacity of offering a satisfactory resolution for the “Gravitational Enigma”; the deep profound realization of “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm wherein the entire physical universe does not constitute a “solid”, “continuous” or “constant” physical reality – but is rather being continuously “created”- “dissolved”- “re-created” and “developed” by this singular higher-ordered UCP (e.g., at the incredible rate of “ $c/2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec⁻¹”) also points at a complete “revolution” of our basic understanding – both of the “microscopic” (subatomic quantum) composition of the basic “building-blocks” of all “objects” or “matter” in the universe, as well as of the “macroscopic” (relativistic) level explaining the “origination”- “sustenance”- “dissolution”- and “development” of the entire physical universe, e.g., from its initial “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals, human-beings and leading up to the Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State of the universe!

First, at the “microscopic” (subatomic quantum) level, based on “G-D’s Physics” new “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, and its ensuing realization that no “atom” or in fact any other subatomic “particle” (or other “entity” or even “force”) can exist “continuously” – as it “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s! In fact, based upon “G-D’s Physics profound “Computational Invariance Principle” and associated “Universal Consciousness Reality” theoretical postulates, we reach the inevitable conclusion that since: a) there exists only one singular higher-ordered “computationally-invariant” “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which exists both “during” its computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (e.g., simultaneously for all of its constituting exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features), and also solely exists “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe!); as opposed to the only “transient” (and “phenomenal”) existence of all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features – which exist only “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s (as solely computed by this singular UCP), but “ceases to exist” and “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s; and b) therefore that the existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel (or any subatomic particle or relativistic object) may only be regarded as representing a “transient” and “phenomenal” manifestation of this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR)! Hence, we reached the inevitable conclusion that: not only there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any two UF’s frames, but in fact that there cannot be any “effect” (or any other “material-causal” interaction/s) between any given UF’s frame/s and any subsequent UF’s frame/s! And therefore that the only means for understanding the ongoing (continuous) “origination”- “sustenance”- and “development” of any given (relativistic or quantum subatomic) object (in the universe) – can only be explained based on a deeper understanding of this singular “Universal Consciousness Reality’s” (UCR’s) intrinsic “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (THCD’s) and associated THCD’s-Universal Computational Formula (UCF)!

An “Axiomatically Constructed, Empirically Verified, Increasingly Unified” (ACEVIU) Scientific Inquiry!

Perhaps it may be appropriate (at this point) to highlight the manner in which Scientific Inquiry evolves –i.e., based upon a continuous process of “Axiomatically Constructed, Empirically Verified, Increasingly Unified” (ACEVIU) broader understanding of the physical reality! We must recognize, as Thomas Kuhn (1962) pointed out that Science undergoes a series of alternations between phases of “Standard Science”, in which Science conforms to a certain “Standard Science” Paradigm in which the Scientific Inquiry (in any given sub-discipline in Science) is based on a given set of axioms and laws constraining and guiding the knowledge and understanding in that given discipline: Such as for instance, Newton’s Classical Mechanics’ set of Axioms and Laws! However, Thomas Kuhn is teaching us that at a certain point along the continuous evolution of our Scientific Inquiry (in that given discipline), we reach a point in which there seems to occur a “Paradigmatic-Crisis”, which is followed by an inevitable “Paradigmatic-Shift” if a few critical conditions are satisfied (above and previously); Indeed, based upon the (above) empirical validation of two (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, we must accept “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) as the New (satisfactory) Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Physics!

An Axiomatic “UCR’s Gematria-Based Continuous Origination of the Universe!

Therefore, we’ve now reached a pivotal “turning-point” in our basic understanding of the true nature, continuous origination, dynamics and development of the entire physical universe by this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR)! We understand that the physical universe does not exist as a “solid”, “continuous” or “constant” “objective” reality, but is rather being continuously “created”, “dissolved”, “re-created” and “developed” based on the UCP’s extremely rapid “Gematria-based” computation of the four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time” for each exhaustive spatial object (e.g., based on its Gematria based alphabetic numeric value – which is also closely related to the Five Initial HCD’s, and their association with the semantic meaning of these letters and HCD’s)! According to “G-D’s Physics” axiomatic description of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP computed the two (initial) “Object-related” physical features of “mass” and “time” based on any given object’s “Gematria alphabetic numeric value/s”

is highly complex (e.g., “transcending” our limited “human-intelligence” – pointing at the “Infinite Intelligence” of this singular UCP/UCR! Thus, for instance, “G-D’s Physics” Axiomatic description of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR may “translate” each exhaustive spatial object’s alphabetic numeric value/s – as “equivalent” to both other “equal-valued” “Gematria-numeric value/s” words, i.e., two different words which possess the same “Gematria-based” analyzed numeric value, are assumed to convey the same semantic meaning! As well as “equivalent reversed alphanumeric symmetry” (e.g., for example the Hebrew first letter’s numeric value of “1” for “א” – which can be “switched” for the final Hebrew Letter’s “n” numeric value of 400!?

From all these extremely complex computations (and considerations), “G-D’s Physics” Axiomatic structure for the origination- sustenance- and development of the whole universe, and all of its constituent exhaustive spatial objects is based on the Tanya’s (Holly Book based on Judaism’s Inner Chassidic Teachings) postulation of the UCP’s (i.e., “G-D’s!) “Ten Makarov” for creating the world – which may be likened to the “highest voltage” “Power-Plant” or “Nuclear Reactor”, through which “G-D” created the whole world and universe in Six Days!

There are (implied) in this new (profound) theoretical new Axiomatic description of the origination of the universe and its complete development from “inanimate matter”, “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards Humanity’s “Perfected Geulah Goal State” at least three extremely significant alterations from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM:

a) “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm!

The universe was not “created” (or “caused”) by any direct (or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the “same”- or “different” UF’s frames), such as for instance the Old “Material-Causal” Big-Bang” nuclear event, or the assumed “evolution” of specific species based on Darwin’s Natural Selection Principle’s (DNSP) direct (or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any given organism and its (assumed) “Challenging Environmental Conditions (CEC, or between specific organism/s genetic composition and assumed interaction with Cosmic Electromagnetic Rays (assumed to “cause” a “random genetic mutation” enabling this particular “mutated” organism to better adapt to this “Challenging

b) The UCP's THCD's-UCF's Ongoing Continuous Origination of the Universe!

Based on "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm's realization that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-physical" interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any (single or multiple) UF's frame/s – but rather that the ongoing continuous "creation" of the entire physical universe (e.g., and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) can only be based upon the UCP's singular (higher-ordered) "pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for "steering" the entire physical universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State", in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of the UCP/UCR and lead a life "aligned" with the UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! According to "G-D's Physics", the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR "executes" and "steers" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" is based upon the UCP's/UCR's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" – "Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF)! Indeed, as can be (clearly) seen from the below "THCD's-UCF" Figure and associated Diagram, the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP computes and "adjusts" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is based upon its "Pre-Planned Geulah Goal" Blueprint Plan depicted (or "encapsulated") within the THCD's-UCF (and associated THCD's Diagram); which indicate that for any given (consecutive) UF's frame/s the UCP simultaneously computes all of its exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") based on those THCD's – specifically based upon the UCP's "Consistency" HCD, computing and "executing" the various aspects of this "Consistency" computation which "steers" the world towards a "Moral Balance" (based on the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle") and "Conscious-Moral Development" (e.g., from "inanimate": matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! So, we realize that the only manner in which the physical universe can be "originated"- "sustained"- and "developed"- is solely based upon the UCP's continuous computation (e.g., so many "trillions" of times per second!) through these THCD's – UCF!

c) "G-D's Physics" Universe's Six Days Creation Hypothesis (USDCH)!

Based on "G-D's Physics" principle negation of the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s), it is understood that the development of the universe – i.e., at any of its "past", "present" (or multiple possible future/s!) is not determined based on any previous "material-causal" physical interactions, but is rather produced solely based on the UCP's origination of every consecutive UF's frame/s, based upon its overall "pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – up to its "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of the UCP/UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! we reach the inevitable (profound) theoretical conclusion wherein it becomes clear that the ongoing "origination", "sustenance" ("dissolution") and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) can only be explained based upon this singular higher-ordered UCP's "arrangement" of all "past", "present" and (one of "multiple possible future/s") UF's based on the "Moral-Choice/s" that each Individual human makes, alongside that Pre-Planned Blueprint Plan of the UCP aimed at attaining the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State"! This also implies that our Old

"Materia-Causal" way of looking at the world – which assumed that everything in the universe can be explained simply based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions: is being replaced by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm's profound new understanding that truly the complete "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of the whole universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) can only be based upon this singular higher-ordered UCP's "Pre-Planned Blueprint Plan"! we realize that just as in a Cinematic-Film scenario we could see a "fast-forward leap" in the "film's time rate", so that within the same (given) "time-interval" (e.g., of for example "one minute") we could see occurrences that would otherwise take a whole "hour"! So, it is stipulated that based on this UCP's singular "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for "steering" the world from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings and up to the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State", the UCP "originated" the universe initially at an "accelerated" rate of creating the entire physical universe within a mere "Six Days" time interval – in accordance with "G-D's Physics" discovered "seven secondary HCD's" including: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Nezach", "Hod", "Yessod" & Malchut"! It is important to note, that this novel hypothesis of "G-D's Physics" is anchored in "G-D's Physics" profound new understanding (and discovery) of the ongoing continuous creation of the universe through these seven secondary HCD's (e.g., which materialize and execute the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's "Preplanned Blueprint Plan" for "steering" the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal"!)

We thus reach a completely new understanding of the true "nature", "origination", "dissolution", "re-computation" and "development" of the entire physical universe that is based upon "G-D's Physics" "Axiomatically Constructed, Empirically Verified, Increasingly Unified" (ACEVIU) new theoretical framework! According to this New "G-D's Physics" ACEVIU theoretical framework, the universe was not created as "caused" by a "random", "material-causal" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor is its ongoing continuous accelerated expansion due to any (purely hypothetical, non-existent) "dark-matter" concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe but which could not be experimentally verified even after two full decades of intensive empirical experimentation?! Nor can all Biological development can be attributed to Darwin's Natural Selection Principle's (DNSP's) assumed "material-causal" ("random") physical interactions! This is because (once again), according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for every consecutive UF's frame/s at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec⁻¹") thereby negating the very possibility of the existence of any such "material-causal" physical interactions in any (single or multiple) UF's frame/s!)

Instead, based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., regarding the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) as more valid (and accurate) than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (GRT & QM's) corresponding predictions; the New "G-D's Physics" ACEVIU theoretical framework points at an entirely different (and "exciting") explanation for the ongoing and continuous "origination" of the entire physical universe by the singular (higher-ordered) UCP – based on its "Preplanned Blueprint Plan" for "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe! Based upon the (abovementioned) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE Critical Prediction – indicating that the (otherwise "unexplained" – assumed 95% purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept which could not be verified experimentally and was in fact discarded and rejected by "G-D's Physics" "Computation-

al Duality Principle"!) points at the centrality of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as associated with the UCP's (singular higher-ordered) Increase in its accelerated rate of the universe's expansion! Indeed, according to this new ACEVIU theoretical framework, the only manner in which the (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is able to explain the continuous "origination"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is based on the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which delineates those THCD's "execution" or "materialization" of the UCP's "steering" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP as the basis for the continuous "origination" (and "manifestation" of this UCP), and is also characterized by those "sublime" UCP's "Characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"; which therefore direct and characterize Humanity's behavior during this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" (which we are in fact "entering" with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm!)

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Cite this article: Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich) (2023) What if Einstein was Right?" G-D's Physics" Fulfills Einstein's Quest! Research & Reviews Journal of Modern Physics. **"G-D'S PHYSICS" NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM Special Issue:** 240-261.

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